

Development of a device to trap soil bacteria capable of degrading organic contaminants such as alkanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons

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HIGHLIGHTS

- BactoTrapS tool developed to capture microbiomes that degrade contaminants in soil.
- α - and β -diversity varies between control and PAH/alkane spiked conditions.
- Specific biodegraders enriched by contaminant spiking.
- Most isolates use spiked contaminant as their sole carbon source.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The microbial biodegradation potential of contaminated sites is critical for efficient bioremediation, particularly through bioaugmentation with microorganisms that degrade organic pollutants. The BactoTrapS tool was developed to select and enrich bacteria tolerant to contaminants and capable of biodegradation directly from soils. It comprises a nylon mesh filled with activated carbon or vermiculite spiked with PAHs (phenanthrene, pyrene, dibenzo-a,h-anthracene) or alkanes (n-hexadecane, cyclohexane), while control traps remained unspiked. After five weeks of soil incubation, spiked traps showed significantly higher mineralisation. Bacterial colonisation was evaluated via CFU counts and 16S rDNA qPCR, revealing increased densities in spiked conditions. Alpha diversity analysis showed reduced diversity in spiked traps, while beta diversity confirmed selective enrichment of genera such as *Mycobacterium* and *Polaromonas* under PAHs, and *Nocardioide*s and *Nocardia* under alkanes. These genera were identified as indicator species for the respective contaminants. qPCR of key biodegradation genes (*PAH-RHD α* , *AlkB*, *CYP153*) revealed elevated gene copy numbers in spiked traps. Most isolates from spiked conditions metabolised phenanthrene and hexadecane as sole carbon sources. BactoTrapS offers a rapid, efficient method to enrich biodegrading bacteria for hydrocarbons and other organic contaminants, promising broad applicability for future remediation efforts.

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1. Introduction

Organic contaminants, such as petroleum hydrocarbons can be found in high concentrations in the environment. Indeed, soils can be contaminated by current and former industrial activities, accidental oil spills, leaks and pipeline breaks, resulting in areas with locally high contamination [1]. Petroleum hydrocarbons, mainly alkanes and polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs), cause major problems that require remediation solutions to limit environmental and human health hazards. In this context, bioremediation using microorganism capabilities to degrade organic contaminants, can be a cost-effective and environmentally friendly alternative [2].

Bacteria have the ability to metabolise hydrocarbons, using them as a carbon and energy source and converting them into non-toxic products (carbon dioxide, water and biomass). In surface soils, the dominant hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria are aerobic. Therefore, bioremediation can require additional stimulation, through oxygen and/or nutrient supplementation but in some cases bioaugmentation (direct inoculation of degrading bacterial strains) yields better results. However, the choice of strains to inoculate can be difficult [3]. Indeed, it seems necessary to isolate bacteria from each site for several reasons. Firstly, legislation on this subject (*in situ* introduction of exogenous microbial strains) varies from country to country, so autochthonous bacteria are more suitable to avoid unpredictable ecological or sanitary impacts. Secondly, these bacterial strains are well adapted to their native soil and have a better chance of developing properly [4,5] compared to exogenous microorganisms. Furthermore, using a consortium rather than individual strains can be more efficient in degrading complex mixtures of hydrocarbons [6–8].

Currently, isolation and enrichment methods mainly consist of growing microorganisms with the contaminant as the sole carbon source in liquid media or agar plates [9,10], although only a small fraction of bacteria can be isolated using these methods. Therefore, there is a need to develop new approaches that closely mimic *in situ* conditions and target degrading and functional consortia rather than individual bacterial strains.

In situ biofilm samplers for rapid collection of biofilms in ground-water monitoring wells were developed by Peacock et al. [11]. Briefly, they consisted of perforated Teflon tubes filled with Bio Sep Beads (made of 75 % powdered activated carbon and 25 % aramid polymer) or glass wool surrounded by ultrafiltration membrane. These samplers were then improved by Geyer et al. [12] by loading the beads with ^{13}C -labelled contaminants to not only collect biofilms but also provide evidence that specific biodegradation of these contaminants is occurring *in situ*. Since then, these so-called biotrapS or BACTRAP®S were used by several teams [13–15] to demonstrate biodegradation, mainly of BTEX or PAHs. However, there is no real equivalent of a bacteria trapping system adapted to the soil environment.

Our aim was to develop a similar tool, adapted to the soil matrix that could be easily used by site owners and managers, and that could capture a large diversity of contaminant-degrading bacteria for a wide range of organic contaminants corresponding to the pollution present *in situ*. This tool is also comparable to litter bag systems, which are mesh bags filled with plant litter that are placed in soils, on site, to estimate microbial activity using decomposition rate as a proxy [16]. To adapt this tool to our needs, the litter was replaced by an inert matrix supplemented with the organic contaminant. As part of the EU-funded MIBIREM project, which aims to develop a microbiome toolbox to facilitate and promote the application of bioremediation, we aimed to develop and validate this new tool, called BactoTrapS. BactoTrapS were tested in microcosm experiments with two types of contamination (a mixture of alkanes and a mixture of PAHs), the trapped bacterial communities were characterized and we demonstrated that the isolation of strains capable of degrading hydrocarbons was facilitated.

2. Material & methods

2.1. Soil sample

A surface soil (2–20 cm depth) was sampled from a natural attenuation area of a former coking plant site (49° 12.54 N, 5° 59.528 E, Homécourt, Grand-Est region, France). Soil was air-dried, sieved to 2.4 mm and stored at room temperature [17]. Soil physico-chemical analyses were carried out at the Laboratoire d'Analyses des Sols (INRAE, Arras, France). Briefly, the soil is sandy (72.1 %) with a pH of 8.2 and total organic carbon and total nitrogen concentrations of 108 and 2.55 g kg⁻¹ DW soil, respectively. Concentrations of the 16 US-EPA priority PAHs concentrations were measured using an Accelerated Solvent Extractor (DIONEX® 200 ASE) and determined by reverse-phase chromatography UHPLC as described in Gréau et al. [18]. The sum of the 16 US-EPA PAHs was 233 ± 45 mg kg⁻¹ DW soil (with low molecular weight PAHs (2–3 cycles) representing 32.2 ± 7 mg kg⁻¹ DW and high molecular weight PAHs (4–6 cycles) representing 200.7 ± 10 mg kg⁻¹ DW). Total petroleum hydrocarbons (C10 to C40 fractions) were measured (Agrolab, Al-West, Deventer, The Netherlands) and represented 330 ± 21 mg kg⁻¹ DW soil (1 % C10-C12, 4 % C12-C16, 20 % C16-C20, 20 % C20-C24, 25 % C24-C28, 18 % C28-C32, 10 % C32-C36 and 2 % C36-C40).

2.2. BactoTrapS manufacturing

Rectangles (5.5 cm x 11 cm) were cut from 20 micron nylon mesh fabric (SEFAR NITEX 03–20/14) and turned inwards to create a tea bag-like device. Two sides were then sealed with a plastic sealer at a temperature of 50°C (Thimonnier S.A, Lyon, France), while the last side was sealed after loading the matrix with the contaminant inside (Fig. 1).

Two matrices with high surface for bacterial colonisation were tested as colonisation support and contaminant adsorbent in the device. On the one hand, vermiculite (V), which is a clay mineral of the phyllosilicate group characterised by a specific surface of 3.0 ± 0.7 m²/g (with 27 % of nanopores <2 nm; adsorption-desorption method with nitrogen 77 K using an absorbometer Belsorp-Max II, MicrotracBEL Corp.), a high water retention capacity. Vermiculite pellets of less than 4 mm were autoclaved before their use. On the other hand, activated carbon (C) pellets with a diameter of 1 mm (commercial product for air and water

Fig. 1. BactoTrapS manufacturing and experimental set-up steps.

purification), were tested, as they are already known for their high pollutant adsorption capacity and activated carbon is used in the aquatic BACTRAP®s devices. Activated carbon has a specific surface of $29.4 \pm 1.4 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ (with 44 % of nanopores $<2 \text{ nm}$) and have a lower water retention capacity than vermiculite. The pellets were rinsed twice with tap water to remove dust particles, then dried under a fume hood and autoclaved before their use.

Each BactoTrapS was loaded with a mass of matrix corresponding to an identical volume of 10 mL (maximal loading capacity of the device) representing 1.2 g for vermiculite and 8.5 g for activated carbon.

Control BactoTrapS were filled with the matrix only, while spiked BactoTrapS containing organic contaminants were prepared. Two mixtures of model hydrocarbons were used for spiking, one as a mixture of 3 model PAH compounds of 3, 4 and 5 benzene rings (solubilised in hexane) and another as a mixture of 2 model alkanes, one linear and one cyclic. The spiked hydrocarbons were added in large excess corresponding to 12.75 mg of phenanthrene (PHE), 4.5 mg of pyrene (PYR) and 0.75 mg of dibenzo-a,h-anthracene (DBA) per BactoTrapS for the PAH mixture. Consequently, the concentration of PHE, PYR and DBA per BactoTrapS, respectively reached 10.63, 3.75 and $0.63 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of DW vermiculite and 1.50, 0.53 and $0.088 \text{ mg}\cdot\text{g}^{-1}$ of DW activated carbon. The alkane mixture contained cyclohexane and n-hexadecane (600 μL each per BactoTrapS). Control and spiked matrices were loaded into the nylon mesh device (after solvent evaporation during 24 h under a fume hood for PAH spiked matrices) before sealing (Fig. 1).

2.3. Incubation of BactoTrapS in soil microcosms

Microcosms were set-up in 125 mL flasks to which 30 g aliquots of contaminated soil were added divided in two layers to surround the BactoTrapS device (Fig. 1). The soil was watered with 6.3 mL of sterile milliQ water to reach 80 % of its water retention capacity (WRC) and the flasks were hermetically sealed with a septum. Six BactoTrapS conditions were tested in triplicate ($n = 3$). Negative controls were filled with matrix only, either vermiculite (Ctl_V) or activated carbon (Ctl_C). Other BactoTrapS were filled with one of the matrices and spiked with the PAH mixture (PAH_V or PAH_C) or the alkane mixture (Alk_V or Alk_C). The flasks were incubated at 24°C , in the dark, for five weeks, and mineralisation monitoring was performed twice a week. Flasks were opened for 30 minutes under a fume hood to renew the internal atmosphere and maintain aerobic conditions just after mineralisation measurements. Humidity was checked by weighing the flasks and adjusted with milliQ water, if necessary.

2.4. Mineralisation monitoring

Carbon dioxide (CO_2) production and oxygen (O_2) levels were measured in each flask twice a week throughout the incubation period to monitor microbial mineralisation activity and to highlight potential contaminant biodegradation. An empty control flask was incubated under the same conditions to allow correction of the gas measurement with atmospheric values. Measurements were performed using an infrared spectrophotometer (Xstream Gas analyzer) by injecting 10 mL of headspace from each flask with a syringe under a nitrogen stream. First, CO_2 level was measured in parts per million (ppm) and then converted by taking the following parameters into account: carbon molar mass (M_C in $\text{g}\cdot\text{mol}^{-1}$), total headspace volume in the flask (HV in L), dilution factor of the apparatus (F), CO_2 molar volume (V_m in L) and soil dry weight (DW) mass (m in g). The following calculation ($\text{CO}_{2(\text{ppm})} \times M_C \times HV \times F$)/($V_m \times m$) was done to express mineralisation activities as the amount of carbon from CO_2 produced per gram of DW soil per day ($\mu\text{g C}\cdot\text{CO}_2 \text{ g}^{-1} \text{ d}^{-1}$). Oxygen content (%) was used only as an indicator of the maintenance of aerobic conditions in the flasks, so these data are not presented.

2.5. Harvesting of BactoTrapS

After five weeks of incubation, the flasks were opened and the BactoTrapS were collected with large sterile forceps. They were dried on paper towels for 15 minutes and brushed to remove soil particles. Then, they were opened with a sterile scalpel and the matrix was poured into a sterile aluminium cup and weighed. A quarter of the content was stored at -20°C for DNA extraction and half was transferred to 9 mL of 0.9 % NaCl solution, for bacterial isolation. The remaining matrix was used to calculate fresh weight vs. dry weight.

2.6. Bacterial isolation and identification from BactoTrapS

Ten-fold serial dilutions, in 0.9 % NaCl, were made from the initial tube containing the matrix in 0.9 % NaCl solution, then plated onto TSB $1/10$ agar medium (Tryptic Soy Broth, Sigma-Aldrich) and incubated for 48–96 h at 24°C . Colony forming units (CFU) were counted and each individual colony from a dilution was repeatedly subcultured on fresh TSB $1/10$ agar plates to allow isolation of pure isolates. Pure isolates were cryopreserved at -80°C with TSB $1/10$ and 20 % glycerol (v/v).

PCR was performed on fresh colony for each isolate to amplify their 16S rDNA genes using the universal primer set 27 F/1492 R [19,20]. The total reaction volume was 30 μL and consisted of 15 μL Phire 2X Master Mix (Thermo Fisher), 0.8 μM of each primer and $0.4 \mu\text{g} \mu\text{L}^{-1}$ of bovine serum albumin (BSA). A negative control was performed with sterile water. After checking their size on a 1 % agarose gel, the amplicons were purified using the Gel and PCR clean-up Nucleospin kit (Macherey Nagel), and sent using the same primer set for forward and reverse Sanger sequencing (Eurofins-Genomics, Germany). Sequences were trimmed to remove ambiguous bases and both forward and reverse complements were aligned and merged before BlastN analysis (NCBI). Sequences were deposited in Genbank under the accession numbers PQ596225 to PQ596291 and PQ592095 to PQ592111.

2.7. Assay to evaluate growth and biodegradation potential of isolates on PAHs and alkanes

Isolates were first grown in TSB $1/10$ liquid medium for one week prior to the growth and biodegradation assays. The cells were then centrifuged at 5000 rpm, washed twice with 0.9 % NaCl to remove traces of rich medium and resuspended in Bushnell-Haas minimal medium. To homogenise the bacterial density in each well, cell suspensions were prepared to achieve a final optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) of 0.1 per well.

The assay was performed in 96-well microtiter plates to monitor the growth and biodegradation of phenanthrene (PHE), hexadecane (Hxd), diesel (Dsl) and glucose (Glu, as positive control) as sole carbon source for each isolate, in triplicate. Negative controls with or without the different carbon source and without cell suspension were run in duplicate to ensure that there was no contamination and to act as a blank for absorbance measurements. Sterile carbon sources solutions (PHE, Hxd, Dsl, and Glu) were prepared to provide 0.3 mg of carbon per well (in 10 μL). PHE, Hxd and Dsl were dissolved in hexane, while Glu was dissolved in sterile milliQ water. PHE, Hxd and Dsl were added to the plate wells and hexane was evaporated for 2 h under a fume hood. The day of the assay, 200 μL of Bushnell-Haas minimal medium (Sigma Aldrich) was added to each well and 10 μL of glucose solution was added to the positive control wells. Cell suspensions (50 μL) were added to the assay wells and 50 μL of 0.9 % NaCl solution was added to the negative controls. The plates were incubated for one week at 24°C on a shaking table.

Optical density at 600 nm (OD_{600}) was monitored using a microtiter plate reader (MP96, SAFAS Monaco) during the incubation from t_0 to t_7 days to assess bacterial growth on each substrate. After one week of incubation, the respiration assay (deshydrogenase activity) was performed by adding 10 μL of WST-1 reagent (Cell proliferation reagent

ready to use, Abcam) per well. The plates were kept in the dark and the optical density at 420 nm (OD_{420}) was measured at 3.5 hours after shaking the microtiter plate for 30 seconds at 1000 rpm. The absorbance of each control was subtracted from the corresponding conditions at $t_{3.5\text{ h}}$ to obtain the change in absorbance. Based on the calculated optical density (OD), categories were created to compare the growth and biodegradation capacities of the isolates. Indeed, an OD below 0.1 indicated no growth nor biodegradation on the substrate and an OD of 0.1–0.3 indicated a low activity. Conversely, moderate growth or biodegradation on the substrate resulted in an OD between 0.3 and 0.6 and OD above 0.6 indicated high growth or biodegradation capabilities.

2.8. DNA extraction

DNA was extracted from frozen aliquots of BactoTrapS matrices (ca. 300 mg) using the Fast DNA spin kit for soil (MP Biomedicals) according to the manufacturer's instructions. DNA purity and concentration were measured using a NanoDrop™ One spectrophotometer (NanoDrop Products, Illkirch, France).

2.9. Real-time quantitative PCR

Bacterial 16S rDNA gene copies were quantified with real-time PCR to assess the bacterial colonisation in each BactoTrapS using the 968 F/1401 R primer set [21]. In addition, genes involved in the biodegradation of the two types of organic pollutants were also quantified to assess the biodegradation potential of the communities. Indeed, the alkane monooxygenase genes *alkB* (*AlkB-1f/AlkB-1r*, [22]), the cytochrome P450 alkane hydroxylases *CYP153A P450* (*P450fw1/P450rv3*, *Van Beilen et al.* [23]) and the PAH ring-hydroxylating dioxygenase genes for both Gram-positive (GP) and Gram-negative (GN) bacteria (*PAH-RHD α* GP F/R and GN F/R, [24]) were quantified. Real-time quantitative PCR assays were performed in a 20 μl reaction volume containing either 2X IQ SYBR Green Supermix (Bio-Rad, CA, USA) for amplification of 16S rDNA, *PAH-RHD α* GP and GN genes or 2X Sso Advanced Universal SYBR Green Supermix (Bio-Rad, CA, USA) for *alkB* and *CYP153A P450* genes, 0.4 μM of each primer, 0.4 $\mu\text{g}\ \mu\text{l}^{-1}$ of bovine serum albumin (BSA), 0.2 μl of dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) and 1 μl of template DNA (used at 10 $\text{ng}\ \mu\text{l}^{-1}$ or at its original concentration if below 10 $\text{ng}\ \mu\text{l}^{-1}$) or distilled water (negative control). Standard plasmids for each real-time quantitative PCR assay were diluted as a 10-fold dilution series from 10^8 to 10^1 target gene copies μl^{-1} , for calibration and absolute quantification.

2.10. 16S rDNA sequencing for metabarcoding and analysis

DNA extracts were sent to Microsynth AG (Balgach, Switzerland) for amplification, library preparation and amplicon sequencing of the V3-V4 region of the 16S rDNA (341 F/805 R) using Illumina MiSeq V2, 2×250 bp. Reads have been deposited in the SRA database under BioProject accession number PRJNA1185691. Reads were processed using R Studio with the packages *dada2* [25], *phyloseq* [26] and custom functions. Sequences were first quality checked by generating a quality profile. Reads were filtered and trimmed according to their quality score using *dada2* with default parameters (`filterAndTrim()` with `truncQ=2` and `maxEE=c(2,2)`), denoised (`derepFastq()`) and merged (`mergePairs()`) to generate an Amplicon Sequence Variant (ASV) table. Chimeras were removed using the *dada2* function `removeBimeraDenovo()`. Finally, taxonomic assignment was performed using the Silva 138 database. Rarefaction curves were plotted to evaluate the completeness of the sequencing. All downstream analyses (alpha and beta diversity) were performed using *phyloseq* on the rarefied data set corresponding to the minimum number of reads per sample (7218 reads) and the centre-log ratio transformed data set.

2.11. Statistical analyses

All statistical analyses and data presentation were performed using R studio software (Rstudio, v4.3.2) or Microsoft Excel. For each test, $p < 0.05$ was used as the significance threshold.

Normality and homogeneity of variance of our data were tested using the Shapiro-Wilk and Bartlett tests, respectively. These parameters determined the application of the following tests to each dataset. In total, statistical analyses were carried out on three datasets, consisting of a global dataset containing all the variables tested and two sub-datasets gathering samples with a similar matrix to avoid matrix effects. One-way ANOVA and Tukey *post-hoc* tests were performed on the bacterial colonisation and mineralisation data. Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn *post-hoc* tests were applied to *PAH-RHD α* GN qPCR data, while one-way ANOVA and Tukey *post-hoc* tests were used to detect significant differences between each condition for the remaining genes. All alpha diversity indices, except *chao1*, were normally distributed with homogeneous variance. Therefore, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey *post-hoc* tests were used for these indices while Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn *post-hoc* tests were used for *chao1* data. Bacterial community composition between samples was compared by non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS based on Bray-Curtis distance matrix and 1000 iterations) and confirmed by analysis of variance (PERMANOVA and *betadisper*) and analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) on sequencing data (1000 permutations). In addition, taxonomic composition between samples was compared at different levels using non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn *post-hoc* tests.

Finally, an indicator species (IS) analysis was performed (*Indicspecies* package from [27] and [28]) on the metabarcoding data to search for differentially abundant species as a function of the contamination variable. As defined by the United Nations Environment Programme an indicator species is a “species that are used as ecological indicators of community or habitat types, environmental conditions or environmental changes.” This analysis was completed with the calculation of a Log2 fold change (Log2FC) value to express the difference in relative abundance of each IS between the hydrocarbon spiked conditions and the controls to highlight the extent of each indicator species enrichment.

3. Results

3.1. Contaminant mineralisation

Aerobic mineralisation activity was measured throughout the incubation period for each condition (Fig. 2). We compared the microbial activity in the control flasks with the flasks containing spiked BactoTrapS and we also compared the two types of matrix used for trapping (vermiculite and activated carbon). The matrix used had no significant effect on the microbial mineralisation activity. Mineralisation activity was significantly higher in contaminant-spiked BactoTrapS compared to unspiked controls for both matrices. Furthermore, the mineralisation activity was higher in flasks containing alkane-spiked BactoTrapS compared to PAH-spiked BactoTrapS. As no carbon source other than the hydrocarbon contaminants was added to the BactoTrapS, the difference in CO_2 production between the controls and the spiked conditions likely corresponds to mineralisation of the added contaminants. After 5 weeks of incubation, this mineralisation difference between the spiked conditions and their respective controls added up to 161, 167, 433, 416 μg of carbon from CO_2 per g of dry weight soil for PAH_V, PAH_C, Alk_V and Alk_C, respectively.

3.2. Bacterial colonisation of BactoTrapS

Bacterial colonisation was assessed by two complementary methods: CFU count (Fig. 3A) and 16S rDNA gene copy number (Fig. 3B). Firstly, a bacterial colonisation of all BactoTrapS matrices was observed irrespective of the presence or absence of the contaminant, with a minimum

Fig. 2. Microbial mineralisation activities in flasks containing BactoTrapS. Comparison of the two matrices: vermiculite (V) and activated carbon (C) and the three conditions: unspiked control (Ctl) in grey, BactoTrapS spiked with PAH mixture (PAH) in orange, and with alkane mixture (Alk) in green. Mean daily mineralisation ($n = 3$) expressed as the amount of carbon from CO₂, produced per gram of soil dry weight per day. Statistical significance was tested using one-way ANOVA tests on both matrices independently and on the global data set (p value < 0.05). Capital letters indicate significant differences between vermiculite conditions, while lower case letters indicate statistical significance between activated carbon conditions. Statistical tests on the global dataset are shown at the top of the figure and significant differences are indicated by an asterisk.

Fig. 3. Bacterial colonisation of BactoTrapS based on CFU count per g of matrix (A) and 16S rDNA gene copy number per g of matrix (B). Data are plotted on a logarithmic scale. Statistical significance was assessed by one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey post-hoc tests for all data sets ($p < 0.05$). Capital letters indicate significant differences between vermiculite conditions, while lower case letters indicate statistical significance between activated carbon conditions. Statistical tests on the global dataset are shown at the top of the figure and significant differences are indicated by asterisks or “ns” if not significant.

of 1.36×10^5 CFU per gram of matrix and 5.52×10^5 16S rDNA copies per gram of matrix. Secondly, the CFU method showed no significant differences except between unspiked controls and alkane-spiked BactoTrapS, which were more bacterially colonised. Thirdly, the qPCR data showed that the BactoTrapS with activated carbon matrices spiked with PAHs or alkanes were significantly more abundantly colonised by bacteria than the unspiked matrices. This trend was not observed for vermiculite alone, but when both matrices were analysed together, the difference was still significant with a mean of 1.25×10^6 16SrDNA gene copy numbers for controls, 1.52×10^7 for PAH and 5.85×10^7 for alkane spiked matrices.

3.3. Quantification of the functional genes involved in the hydrocarbon biodegradation of the bacteria colonising the BactoTrapS

The biodegradation potential of each bacterial community enriched in the different BactoTrapS was assessed using a qPCR approach with

different primers targeting functional genes (Fig. 4). Indeed, the PAH-ring hydroxylating dioxygenases have been shown to play a crucial role in the PAH biodegradation pathway [24] and the alkane monooxygenase (*alkB* genes) and the cytochrome P450 alkane hydroxylase (*CYP153*) have both been described in the alkane biodegradation pathways [29,30]. Overall, we observed a significant increase in the functional genes associated with the contaminant added to the BactoTrapS. Indeed, *PAH-RHDα GP* genes (present in Actinobacteria) and alkane biodegradation genes were found in higher copy numbers in PAH- and alkane-spiked BactoTrapS, respectively. *PAH-RHDα GP* genes represented 2.08×10^5 to 1.85×10^6 copies per gram of matrix in PAH-spiked BactoTrapS, whereas only 2.23×10^2 to 3.40×10^3 copies per gram of matrix were detected in controls. Surprisingly, the presence of alkane in the BactoTrapS also favoured the development of bacteria carrying these PAH degradation genes. For the *PAH-RHDα GN* gene (present in Proteobacteria), the number of copies quantified was quite low, resulting in high standard errors that severely affected the

Fig. 4. Quantification of genes related to PAH (*PAH-RHDα GP (A)* and *PAH-RHDα GN (B)*) and alkane (*alkB (C)* and *CYP153 (D)*) biodegradation, plotted on a logarithmic scale. Kruskal-Wallis test was performed on *PAH-RHDα GN* gene copies and one-way ANOVA were done for the other genes to assess statistical significance ($p < 0.05$). Capital letters indicate significant differences between vermiculite (V) conditions, while lower case letters indicate statistical significance between activated carbon (C) conditions. In addition, statistical tests on the global data set are shown at the top of the figure and significant differences are indicated by an asterisk or 'ns' if not significant.

Fig. 5. Alpha diversity indices Chao1 (A), Shannon (B) and Pielou evenness (C) indices compared between sample conditions (mean of $n = 3$). Statistical tests ($pvalue < 0.05$) were performed on a global data set and on matrix-separated datasets to remove matrix effects. For each data set, one-way ANOVA followed by Tukey post-hoc was performed for Shannon and Pielou's evenness indices, while non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test followed by Dunn post-hoc was performed for chao1 index. Capital letters indicate significant differences between vermiculite conditions, while lower case letters indicate statistical significance between activated carbon conditions. An asterisk indicates statistical differences between samples in the global dataset, while 'ns' indicates no statistical difference.

Fig. 6. Characterisation of the bacterial community composition depending on the sample conditions through non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) ordination (A) and analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) on contamination (B) and matrix (C) variables. NMDS and ANOSIM (pv alue <0.05, 1000 permutations) were performed using Bray-Curtis dissimilarity distances.

statistical tests, so no significant difference was found. We also found that the gene copy number of both *AlkB* and *CYP153* genes increased significantly in alkane-spiked samples going from 1.00×10^4 to 6.22×10^4 copies per gram of matrix in controls to 4.73×10^5 to 9.19×10^5 copies per gram of matrix in alkane-spiked conditions for *AlkB* and from 7.36×10^3 to 8.66×10^4 copies per gram of matrix in controls to 3.35×10^5 to 7.77×10^5 copies per gram of matrix in alkane-spiked conditions for *CYP153*.

3.4. Alpha- and beta-diversity of trapped bacterial communities

Changes in the diversity of bacteria captured on BactoTrapS with and without contaminant were investigated using 16S rDNA metabarcoding. The sequencing data were rarefied to 7218 reads per sample. Alpha diversity is described by the Chao1 richness index, the Shannon diversity index and the Pielou evenness index (Fig. 5). The Chao1 index was not significantly different between controls and BactoTrapS spiked with PAHs and alkanes (Fig. 5A). The Shannon diversity (Fig. 5B) and Pielou's evenness (Fig. 5C) indices were significantly reduced in spiked samples compared to the controls, with no significant difference between PAH and alkane spiked BactoTrapS.

Bacterial beta diversity was described using non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS) analysis (Fig. 6A). The homogeneity of variance was statistically assessed and was not homogeneous between the groups tested (Betadisper test with $p < 0.05$). Indeed, a higher intra-replicate variability was observed for both types of unspiked controls compared to the spiked conditions, where the diversity between replicates was similar. Most conditions are well separated on the ordination,

indicating that the community composition differed depending on the matrix and the presence or absence of contaminants, except for the two alkane conditions where the community composition overlapped. Furthermore, analysis of similarity (ANOSIM) indicated a significant effect of the contaminant addition (Fig. 6B, $R=0.636$, $p = 0.000999$) on the bacterial community composition as the dissimilarity ranks were higher between than within spiking conditions. An ANOSIM was also performed on the matrix variable and indicated a less significant effect of this parameter (Fig. 6C, $R=0.168$, $p = 0.036963$). Moreover, permutational multiple analysis of variance (PERMANOVA) estimated that the presence of the contaminants explained 22 % of the variation between samples, but this was minimised due to non-homogeneous variance between conditions. In addition, the effect of matrix on community composition was assessed using similar tests and showed that less than 9 % of the variation could be significantly explained by the type of matrix used in BactoTrapS.

The taxonomic composition of the bacterial communities trapped in the different BactoTrapS was presented at the class (Fig. 7A) and genus (Fig. 7B) level. The initial soil taxonomic composition was also provided at the class level (Fig. 7A) to compare with the communities trapped in the BactoTrapS. The taxonomic composition of the communities varied between samples, and the relative abundance of some families and genera increased or decreased. In the initial soil, 20 classes were found to have a relative abundance above 1 % while only 7 classes were identified in the BactoTrapS samples. Moreover, 5 out of these 7 classes were part of the most abundant classes in the initial soil.

In the control BactoTrapS, the families and genera representing less than 1 % were numerous and represented on average 39–53 % of the

Fig. 7. Taxonomic composition at class (A) and genus (B) level depending on BactoTraps sample conditions and initial soil taxonomic composition at class level (A). Mean of 3 replicates for BactoTraps conditions and mean of 5 replicates for the initial soil composition. Only classes and genera representing at least 1 % in relative abundance are shown, those representing less than 1 % are grouped and labelled “Others”. The classes Bacteroidia, Cyanobacteriia and Saccharimonadia were abbreviated as “Bactero.,” “Cyano.” and “Sacch.,” respectively. Genera *Pseudarthrobacter* and *Arthrobacter* were grouped as their V3-V4 16S rRNA regions are 100 % homologous. Kruskal-Wallis and Dunn *post hoc* tests were performed to highlight significant differences between samples.

Table 1

Indicator species linked to PAH- and alkane- spiked conditions with their fold change values (Log2FC) when comparing spiked vs. unspiked control conditions, and the statistical significance represented with asterisks ($p < 0.05$ *, $p < 0.01$ **, $p < 0.001$ ***), ^aPatescibacteria phylum.

Condition	Enriched class	Genus (number of ASV)	Log2 FC	Significance level	
PAH-spiked	Actinobacteria	<i>Kocuria</i> (1)	14.8	*	
		<i>Mycobacterium</i> (6)	6.1–17.1	* to ***	
		<i>Pseudarthrobacter-Arthrobacter</i> (2)	2.9–16.2	*, **	
		<i>Pseudonocardia</i> (1)	2.2	*	
	Gammaproteobacteria	<i>Caenimonas</i> (1)	5.2	**	
		NA (1)	11.5	*	
		<i>Polaromonas</i> (2)	5.2–15.5	*, ***	
		<i>Steroidobacter</i> (1)	3.7	*	
		<i>Xylophilus</i> (1)	3.2	**	
		<i>Devosia</i> (1)	2.0	*	
	Alphaproteobacteria	<i>Ellin6055</i> (1)	9.1	**	
		<i>Ensifer</i> (1)	1.9	*	
		NA (1)	15.5	*	
		<i>Sphingomonas</i> (1)	1.2	*	
		<i>TM7a</i> (2)	14.2–17.3	*, ***	
	Saccharimonadia	<i>Bacili</i>	<i>Tumebacillus</i> (1)	2.5	*
		Actinobacteria	<i>Amycolatopsis</i> (1)	6.3	**
	Alkane-spiked	Actinobacteria	<i>Blastococcus</i> (2)	2.7–2.8	*, **
			<i>Knoellia</i> (1)	3.4	*
<i>Kribbella</i> (1)			3.0	**	
<i>Lechevalieria</i> (1)			16.5	*	
<i>Marmoricola</i> (2)			7.2–14.8	*, **	
<i>Modestobacter</i> (1)			4.6	*	
NA (2)			3.9–15.9	*, ***	
<i>Nocardia</i> (4)			3.9–13.7	* to **	
<i>Nocardioides</i> (12)			2.2–12.6	* to ***	
<i>Pseudarthrobacter-Arthrobacter</i> (1)			3.3	*	
<i>Streptomyces</i> (2)			2.0–2.9	**	
NA (5)			9.6–16.8	* to ***	
<i>TM7a</i> (3)			6.8–14.8	* to ***	
Gammaproteobacteria			<i>Burkholderia-Caballeronia-Paraburkholderia</i> (1)	11.8	*
		<i>Cupriavidus</i> (3)	4.8–16.2	*	
		<i>Ralstonia</i> (1)	15.3	**	
Alphaproteobacteria		<i>Brevundimonas</i> (1)	5.2	*	
		NA (1)	13.1	**	
		<i>Sphingomonas</i> (1)	5.5	*	
Bacteroidia		<i>Chitinophaga</i> (2)	5.5–16.9	*	
Chloroflexia		NA (1)	6.0	*	
ABY1 ^a		NA (1)	11.6	*	

total community, while in the spiked conditions they represented only 19–33 % on average. In fact, these families, grouped in the “Others” group, were significantly more abundant in the controls than in the spiked conditions.

The community in PAH-spiked BactoTrapS showed a significantly higher relative abundance of *Saccharimonadaceae* (*TM7a* genus), *Mycobacteriaceae* (*Mycobacterium* genus) and *Sphingomonadaceae* (*Ellin6055* genus). In addition, other genera such as *Polaromonas* (*Comamonadaceae*) and *Kocuria* (*Micrococcaceae*) were represented in significantly higher relative abundance under PAH-spiked conditions.

For alkane-spiked BactoTrapS, a significantly higher relative abundance of *Burkholderiaceae* (*Cupriavidus* and NA genera), *Caulobacteraceae* (*Brevundimonas* genus), *Geodermatophilaceae* (*Blastococcus* and *Modestobacter* genera), *Nocardioideae* (*Nocardioides* and *Marmoricola* genera), *Nocardiaceae* (*Nocardia* genus), *Pseudonocardiaceae* (*Lechevalieria* genus) and *Saccharimonadaceae* (*TM7a* genus) was detected.

3.5. Identification of indicator species

An indicator species analysis was performed to retrieve species that were significantly more abundant in each of the spiked conditions compared to the controls (Table 1). 24 and 50 indicator species were found to be significantly more abundant in the PAH and alkane spiked conditions, respectively. Among these indicator species, members of Actinobacteria were the most abundant with 10 out of 24 and 31 out of 50 species for PAH- and alkane-spiked conditions, respectively. Members of Alpha- and Gamma-proteobacteria were then identified, as well

as members of the Saccharimonadia. Furthermore, some genera were identified with both contaminants such as *Arthrobacter-Pseudarthrobacter*, *TM7a* or *Sphingomonas*, while others were found specifically with one type of contaminant, such as *Mycobacterium* with PAHs and *Cupriavidus* or *Nocardioides* with alkanes. To further assess the extent of the genus enrichment in spiked conditions, the Log2 fold change (Log2FC) was calculated between spiked conditions and controls. Most genera showed a log2FC at least above 2 and some genera even reached a log2FC above 16, indicating a large difference in abundance compared to the controls.

3.6. Diversity of isolates and their growth and activity on minimal media supplemented with PAHs and alkanes

A total of 84 strains were successfully isolated representing 42 strains for both PAH- and alkane-spiked samples (Table 2). Although strains belonging to the same species were isolated, 14 different species were identified, of which more than half belonged to Actinobacteria (48 strains) while the rest were β - and γ -Proteobacteria. Strains belonging to the genus *Pseudarthrobacter* were isolated from both PAH- and alkane-spiked samples whereas strains belonging to the genus *Arthrobacter* were more PAH-specific. Note that these two genera could not be differentiated based on V3-V4 region of the 16S rDNA in metabarcoding data. In addition, strains belonging to the genera *Cupriavidus*, *Cellulomonas* and *Rhodococcus* were more alkane-specific.

Microbial growth on minimal medium supplemented with PHE or Hxd was measured after one week, but resulted in very low OD₆₀₀

Table 2

Respiration activity assay using phenanthrene (PHE) and hexadecane (Hxd) as the sole carbon source for the 84 isolates from PAH and alkane spiked BactoTrapS. Optical density at 420 nm was measured in triplicate to calculate the mean for each condition and corrected by subtracting the corresponding control. OD420 is highlighted in white if below 0.1 (no activity), in light grey between 0.1 and 0.3 (low activity), in grey between 0.3 and 0.6 (medium activity) and in dark grey if above 0.6 (high activity).

NCBI blast identification	Name	BactoTrapS spiked with	OD WST-1 with PHE	OD WST-1 with Hxd
<i>Arthrobacter ginsengisoli</i>	H1-1	PAHs	0.779	0.929
	H1-20	PAHs	0.522	0.690
	A1-10	Alkanes	0.474	0.433
	A1-13	Alkanes	0.494	0.845
	A1-14A	Alkanes	0.464	0.336
	A2-1	Alkanes	0.551	0.456
	A2-13	Alkanes	0.430	0.478
	A2-14	Alkanes	0.546	0.767
	A3-3A	Alkanes	0.810	0.952
	A3-3B	Alkanes	0.780	0.865
	A3-4	Alkanes	0.327	0.546
	A3-10	Alkanes	0.352	0.654
A3-11	Alkanes	0.472	0.441	
<i>Arthrobacter globiformis</i>	H1-15	PAHs	0.331	0.287
	H1-16	PAHs	0.326	0.283
	H1-27	PAHs	0.545	0.442
	H2-6	PAHs	0.361	0.261
	H2-19	PAHs	0.373	0.553
	H3-7	PAHs	0.324	0.841
	H3-9	PAHs	0.518	0.375
	A3-7	Alkanes	0.197	0.248
<i>Arthrobacter humicola</i>	H2-2	PAHs	0.518	0.302
	H2-22	PAHs	0.397	0.501
	H2-23	PAHs	0.417	0.492
	A1-5	Alkanes	0.684	1.434
<i>Arthrobacter oryzae</i>	H1-29	PAHs	0.236	0.751
	H3-10B	PAHs	0.609	0.421
<i>Arthrobacter pascens</i>	H1-9	PAHs	0.136	0.700
	H1-10	PAHs	0.697	0.728
	H1-11	PAHs	0.677	0.551
	H1-14	PAHs	0.764	0.899
	H1-17	PAHs	0.423	0.585
	H1-18	PAHs	0.561	0.761
	H1-22	PAHs	0.359	0.388
	H1-23	PAHs	0.636	0.300
	H1-24	PAHs	0.896	0.265
	H1-25	PAHs	0.353	0.442
	H1-28	PAHs	0.332	0.617
	H2-1	PAHs	1.085	0.153
	H2-5	PAHs	0.684	0.668
	H2-9	PAHs	0.869	0.366
	H2-24	PAHs	0.471	0.559
	H3-1	PAHs	0.461	0.422
	H3-6	PAHs	0.213	0.596
	H3-8	PAHs	0.478	0.689
H3-12	PAHs	0.520	1.363	
H3-14	PAHs	0.666	1.196	
<i>Cellulomonas pakistanensis</i>	A3-1	Alkanes	0.601	1.228
	A1-14B	Alkanes	0.351	0.261
<i>Cupriavidus campinensis</i>	A1-8	Alkanes	0.193	0.169
	A1-17A	Alkanes	0.140	0.386
	A1-17B	Alkanes	0.138	0.299
	A1-18	Alkanes	0.138	0.255
	A1-19A	Alkanes	0.160	0.281
	A1-19B	Alkanes	0.108	0.244
	A1-20A	Alkanes	0.139	0.284
	A1-20B	Alkanes	0.156	0.376
	A1-20C	Alkanes	0.136	0.347
	A1-21	Alkanes	0.121	0.294
	A1-22	Alkanes	0.121	0.272
	A2-2	Alkanes	0.075	0.492
	A2-4	Alkanes	0.102	0.306
	A3-2A	Alkanes	0.112	0.536
	A3-2B	Alkanes	0.085	0.399
	A3-12A	Alkanes	0.279	0.177
A3-12B	Alkanes	0.239	0.141	
<i>Cupriavidus respiraculi</i>	A1-15	Alkanes	0.150	0.451
	A1-23	Alkanes	0.054	0.296
<i>Massilia niastensis</i>	H1-21	PAHs	0.175	0.154
	H2-3	PAHs	2.539	0.523
<i>Pseudarthrobacter polychromogenes</i>	H2-12	PAHs	0.409	0.891
	H3-5	PAHs	0.406	0.382
	H3-10A	PAHs	0.629	0.572
<i>Pseudarthrobacter psychrotolerans</i>	H1-5	PAHs	0.517	0.678
	A1-1	Alkanes	0.464	0.873
	A2-7	Alkanes	0.227	0.855
	A2-15	Alkanes	0.347	0.615
	A2-17	Alkanes	0.402	0.546
	A3-6A	Alkanes	0.340	0.637
<i>Pseudarthrobacter siccitolerans</i>	A3-9	Alkanes	0.405	0.694
	H3-13	PAHs	0.424	0.252
<i>Pseudarthrobacter sulfonivorans</i>	H2-13	PAHs	1.900	0.706
	A1-11	Alkanes	0.132	0.424
<i>Rhodococcus oxybenzonivorans</i>	A1-11	Alkanes	0.132	0.424
	A1-16	Alkanes	0.448	1.494

(below 0.1 for most isolates, see Table S1), indicating a slow growth on these substrates. Similar results were observed for growth on different PAHs by Johnsen et al. [31] and Thomas et al. [32]. Although microbial growth in minimal medium containing PAH and alkane was slow, respiration activity was successfully recorded and allowed characterization of the isolates (Table 2). Despite some variation, the strains belonging to the same species tended to behave very similarly. Most of the strains were able to use, more or less efficiently, each contaminant as a sole carbon source, but also showed a preference for one type of contaminant, resulting in different activity levels depending on the substrate. Looking at OD above 0.3 (medium and high degradation activity), we found that 69.05 % and 73.81 % of the strains were able to efficiently use PHE and hexadecane as sole carbon source, respectively. Overall, the strains showing the best biodegradation activity with a contaminant were those originally isolated from BactoTrapS spiked with the same contaminant. Indeed, 38 out of 42 strains isolated from PAH-spiked BactoTrapS were able to degrade phenanthrene and similarly 29 out of 42 strains isolated from alkane-spiked BactoTrapS were able to degrade Hxd efficiently. Interestingly, most of the strains collected from the PAH-spiked BactoTrapS that were able to utilise phenanthrene were also able to utilise Hxd (35 strains out of 42). To a lesser extent, this was also observed for strains isolated from alkane-spiked conditions, as 20 out of 42 strains were able to degrade PHE. Looking at the strains collected from alkane-spiked BactoTrapS, we found that *Cupriavidus* strains were only able to degrade Hxd, whereas *Rhodococcus oxybenzonivorans* and *Pseudarthrobacter psychrotolerans* degraded Hxd more efficiently and were also able to utilise Diesel (see Table S2).

4. Discussion

Our new BactoTrapS tool, when incubated directly in contaminated soil, successfully trapped hydrocarbon tolerant and hydrocarbon degrading bacteria. Firstly, the effectiveness of BactoTrapS was demonstrated by the lower specific richness and diversity of the bacterial communities colonising the spiked BactoTrapS compared to the controls and the initial soil. Reduced richness and diversity indicate that, part of the community has been selected by the contaminant. Within the soil bacterial community, only certain bacteria were able to colonise BactoTrapS as some are attracted to hydrocarbons by known chemotaxis mechanisms [33,34]. The bacteria that grow on the surface of the BactoTrapS matrices have the ability to use hydrocarbons (alkanes and PAHs) as their sole carbon source, giving them a growth advantage, but as it's known that less than 10 % of the bacteria present in hydrocarbon contaminated environments are able to degrade hydrocarbons [35], it explains the lower diversity in the BactoTrapS. Secondly, the captured bacterial community carried well known hydrocarbon-degrading genes. The *PAH-RHD α* , *alkB* and *CYP450* genes are well known to be involved in hydrocarbon degradation pathways in a large number of isolated bacteria [24,36,30]. Moreover, there was a significant enrichment of the genera *Mycobacterium*, *Polaromonas* and members of *Sphingomonadaceae* on the PAH-spiked BactoTrapS and a significant enrichment of many members of the Actinobacteria (*Nocardioides* and *Nocardia*) as well as Alpha and Beta-Proteobacteria (*Brevundimonas* and *Cupriavidus*) among the taxa trapped on alkane-spiked BactoTrapS, all of which are known for their potential to biodegrade PAHs [37,38] or alkanes [6,39–41]. In addition, some genera (*Pseudarthrobacter*, *Arthrobacter* and *TM7A*) were isolated and identified as indicator species in both types of spiked BactoTrapS indicating that they carry biodegradation-related genes for both contaminants, as it was previously shown for *Pseudomonas* strains by Guermouche M' rassi et al. [42]. Thirdly, we were able to isolate strains capable to grow on PAHs or alkanes as the sole carbon source, from BactoTrapS matrices, using a non-selective medium. This finding shows the enrichment of strains capable of degrading hydrocarbons trapped into the BactoTrapS and demonstrates the effectiveness of our new trapping system.

However, it is interesting to note that some lesser-known genera were also captured on both PAH- and alkane- spiked BactoTrapS, such as representatives of *TM7a* belonging to the *Saccharimonadaceae* and some Actinobacteria (*Kocuria*, *Blastococcus*, *Modestobacter*, *Marmoricola* and *Lechevalieria*) which have never or rarely been isolated for their ability to biodegrade hydrocarbons and could possess unknown functional pathways [43,44]. Indeed, some of the bacteria growing in BactoTrapS may not directly degrade the contaminant, but may i) be tolerant to hydrocarbons and use intermediate metabolites released by the primary degraders for their growth [29,45], which could potentially inhibit the growth of other bacteria [46,47], or ii) be considered as helper bacteria in the community by producing co-metabolites or biosurfactants that increase the solubility and/or bioavailability of the contaminants [48]. The use of BactoTrapS therefore allows a much greater diversity of bacteria to be captured than the approach commonly used to isolate hydrocarbon-degrading bacteria (enrichment in liquid or on agar medium supplemented with hydrocarbons).

This strategy aims to enrich microorganisms before isolating them and has several advantages: i) it is time-saving, as it is not necessary to isolate hundreds of strains to identify a few degraders as Harayama et al. [49] reported that even in contaminated environments, bacteria capable of degrading hydrocarbons often represent 1–10 % of the total microbial community; ii) it allows to skip the enrichment step in liquid medium, which tends to strongly select for bacteria that can develop well in liquid medium. In fact, it is well known that traditional enrichment methods in liquid media significantly underestimate microbial diversity because many soil bacteria cannot grow in such an artificial laboratory condition. They are not adapted to liquid conditions because they do not have an aquatic lifestyle and that the complex nature of soil interactions and microenvironments cannot be reproduced in a liquid medium [50,51]. And iii) BactoTrapS provide similar conditions to soils, allowing a greater diversity of bacteria to be trapped and potentially isolated or efficient microbial consortia to be directly extracted. Therefore, our strategy was successful and is promising for further applications to trap and isolate not only bacterial degraders but also fungi or even archaea by using a variety of organic contaminants (other hydrocarbons, pesticides, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances, ...).

As a first attempt, we remained non-selective by using rich media without selective pressure to maximise the chances of isolating a wide diversity of bacteria and then testing their biodegradation capacity to assess the percentage of hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria in our collection. For future use, we recommend using a combination of different culture media to isolate a greater diversity of bacteria, as we saw that the diversity of bacteria colonizing the BactoTrapS was higher when examined by metabarcoding compared to the bacterial isolates we purified from a single rich medium. For example, we identified bacterial genera belonging to the *Saccharimonadaceae*, as well as a large diversity of Actinobacteria representatives that could not be isolated. Saccharibacteria, formerly known as candidate division TM7, are considered as part of the "microbial dark matter" because they were mostly identified by 16SrRNA sequencing rather than cultivation. They are ultra-small bacteria with a small genome size, which limits their synthetic capabilities, and may be obligate symbionts or parasites of other organisms, including bacteria [52]. They may need to be grown under oligotrophic conditions, on medium supplemented with growth factors or metabolic intermediates, to be co-cultured with their host, or grown under anaerobic or microaerophilic conditions. For actinobacteria in particular, the challenge is to select media that favour their growth while inhibiting the growth of faster growing bacteria or fungi. The use of Actinomycete isolation agar (AIA) or humic acid-vitamin agar (HV) media could help, but there are a number of media specifically designed for *Streptomycetes* that could also be used. On these media, it is recommended to maintain the selective pressure by adding a sublayer of the contaminant mixture on top of the medium to select for tolerant and/or degrading bacteria. In addition, we could have targeted other microorganisms such as fungi or archaea with adapted media.

In these experiments, both inert matrices used for BactoTrapS gave satisfactory results, but we recommend continuing to use vermiculite as the matrix. Indeed, although the specific surface is lower than the activated carbon, the vermiculite has a greater capacity to retain water and contaminants and the colonisation surface for microorganisms is higher (less nanopores non accessible to bacteria), hence a higher bacterial abundance was observed with this matrix. Vermiculite has a lamellar, porous structure that enables it to retain large amounts of water and air, which is essential for maintaining constant humidity and good gas exchange, conditions that are favourable for the growth of microorganisms. In addition, vermiculite is mineral, being a type of clay, and therefore more representative of soil materials. Vermiculite tends to be neutral or slightly alkaline, which may be more suitable for bacteria from soils contaminated with organic compounds, which often tend to be alkaline [53]. Vermiculite has been used as an inert carrier for microbial inoculums. For example, it can be impregnated with a nutrient solution and/or a microbial inoculum (such as nitrogen-fixing bacteria or mycorrhizal fungi) to promote microbial colonisation and be used for fertilisation or bioaugmentation in agriculture [54]. Vermiculite inoculated with hydrocarbonoclastic microorganisms has already been used as an amendment for hydrocarbon-contaminated soils, mainly for its ability of support and to stabilise microbial populations under difficult soil conditions [55].

The BactoTrapS could have been incubated *in situ*, but a number of constraints led us to prefer laboratory incubation for optimal results. Firstly, as they contain contaminants, we believe it is preferable to incubate them in the soil sampled *in situ* at the sites of interest, but using small amounts of soil, rather than risk further contamination of the environment. Furthermore, *in situ* incubation would only have been possible in the surface soils, with no control over the incubation conditions (depending on the weather at the time of incubation) and therefore no way of predicting the incubation period. The advantage of incubation in the laboratory is that we can work on all types of soil (surface samples or samples taken from several metres below the surface) and choose the conditions for capturing the microorganisms: optimum humidity conditions, and the possibility of regulating the atmosphere in the microcosms if the aim is to capture anaerobic microorganisms, for example.

5. Conclusion

In this study, we developed and tested the efficacy of a new tool, called BactoTrapS, designed to provide an alternative approach to selectively enrich and isolate hydrocarbon tolerant or biodegrading bacteria from a contaminated soil. This tool contained a matrix (vermiculite or activated carbon), spiked with either a mixture of PAHs or alkanes, and was incubated in soil microcosms for several weeks. We were able to show that, depending on the contaminant spiked, the bacterial communities, captured by the BactoTrapS, were specifically adapted to the contamination. Indeed, the bacterial diversity was reduced in spiked conditions and we noted a dominance of known PAHs or alkanes degrading bacterial taxa. Moreover, bacteria carried genes involved in hydrocarbon biodegradation pathways, indicating a high biodegradation potential of these communities. Finally, a total of 84 bacterial strains were isolated from the BactoTrapS and most presented high capacities to use phenanthrene and/or hexadecane as sole carbon source. Therefore, BactoTrapS proved to be efficient and could represent an easy to use and affordable method to assess biodegradation potential directly *in situ*, to enrich and then isolate hydrocarbonoclastic bacteria or consortia that could be further used for bioaugmentation in bioremediation strategies. This tool is currently used with other organic contaminants (hexachlorocyclohexane mixture and diesel) and its applications are very broad, given the huge diversity of organic contaminants present in soils (pesticides, pharmaceutical compounds, per- and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS), etc.). It could also be perfectly suited for the enrichment and isolation of fungi, or bacterial-fungal consortia.

Environmental implication

Soil contamination by hydrocarbons is a global issue requiring effective bioremediation solutions. To make these approaches more accessible, rapid tools are needed to enrich and isolate hydrocarbon-degrading microorganisms. The goal is to enrich microbiomes (microbial consortia with complementary metabolisms) that degrade complex, mixed contaminants found in soils more efficiently than single strains. Our new device, BactoTrapS, offers a versatile solution to enrich microbiomes capable of degrading a wide range of organic pollutants, not just hydrocarbons. This innovative tool has the potential to significantly advance bioremediation strategies for various contaminated sites in the future.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Cébron Aurélie: Writing – review & editing, Validation, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Investigation, Funding acquisition, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Vauloup Audrey:** Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137690](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jhazmat.2025.137690).

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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